

Systematic review on valuation uptake

Valuation uptake review sample documentation

Author: David Barton

Introduction

This document contains a description of the Chapter 4 sample for the valuation uptake review, based on the May version of the Chapter 3 & Chapter 4 shared corpus.

The note also contains the approach to stratification, a proposal for assigning papers to reviewers, and the STATA script used to generate the sample.

Context: Chapter 3 and Chapter 4 differences in scoping of valuation applications

Chapter 4 search terms mean that if the study did not have a method family specific keyword in Methods Family 1-4 (TS 8, 9, 10, 11 in the *Table 1* of the DMR¹) it was not included in the random sample. The rationale for this choice was that Method Family keywords represent primary valuation method applications, whereas Methods A and Methods B are descriptors of the valuation methods process/results and therefore mostly redundant in relation to identifying valuation method applications.

What are the implications? Chapter 4's scope for identifying valuation applications is therefore narrower than Chapter 3's. What are some examples of narrower scope? For example, studies were not identified as valuation applications for the Chapter 4 valuation uptake review if the title-abstract refers

- e.g., only "willingness-to-pay" (Method A) but not a method such as "contingent valuation"; or
- e.g., only "benefit transfer" but not to one of the monetary valuation methods (Method Family 2,3); or
- e.g., only "stakeholder workshop" (Method B) but not to "deliberative valuation" (Method Family 2); or
- e.g., only "participatory GIS" (Method B), but not to "participatory mapping" (Method Family 2); or
- e.g., only "narrative method" (Method B), but not "biocultural method" (Method Family 2).

We acknowledge that this interpretation may have excluded some applied valuation method types identified only in Method A and Method B search terms that could be important for the study of valuation uptake, in particular:

- benefit/value transfers that don't have any reference in the abstract to primary method types being transferred

¹ Systematic review on valuation uptake (10.5281/zenodo.4391335)

- Bayesian belief networks (BN, BBN) that integrate valuation, without reference to the methods they are integrating
- Participatory GIS-based methods
- Q-method
- Narrative methods

What could be the bias of Chapter 4 valuation uptake review results relative to Chapter 3? Due to our narrower scoping we may find excessively low uptake if it is true that benefit transfer, BBNs, GIS-based methods, Q-method and narrative methods are more likely to document stakeholder uptake. For example, environmental economics research proposes that benefits transfer is a highly applied valuation method appropriate for stakeholder decision-support. Participatory GIS-based ecosystem service mapping methods would by definition be uptake studies because stakeholders participate. Q and narrative methods may similarly be defined as high uptake to the extent that stakeholders are interviewed.

Note also that the search terms for the corpus shared between Chapter 3 and Chapter 4 is not necessarily exhaustive. For example, “ecosystem service mapping” was not used as a search term, although more specific methods were, such as “ESTIMAP”.

Description of Chapter 4 sample (June 2020)

Analysis: gen multi_method = TS20 + TS21 + TS22 + TS23 /* does the study use multiple methods? */

method_number	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
0	34,081	43.12	43.12
1	43,422	54.94	98.06
2	1,463	1.85	99.91
3	73	0.09	100.00
4	1	0.00	100.00
Total	79,040	100.00	

Result

>> 43% of the corpus has no method keyword hits, 54% has one method keyword hit, 2% of sample appear to be multiple valuation method studies:

>> stratification on a single method will perhaps exclude multi-method studies. Multi-method studies should be sampled as a particular stratum to evaluate H1: multi-method studies have a higher likelihood of uptake

>> for chapter 4 none of the studies without method reference are in scope following the logic no method -> no valuation outputs to uptake. They are dropped from the Chapter4 sample.

>> Chapter 4 universe. Valuation method applications

Strata (June 10th)

Methods with a single or multiple method application keywords N = 44959. The following strata are mutually exclusive. All strata except “multi-method” belong to one method family TS20-TS23.

strata_methods	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
biophysical(TS20)	31,737	70.59	70.59
integrating(TS23)	3,211	7.14	77.73
multi-method	1,537	3.42	81.15
revealed(TS22)	3,576	7.95	89.11
stated(TS21)	4,898	10.89	100.00
Total	44,959	100.00	

> proportional sampling will make it 71% likely to review biophysical methods. For this reason, Chapter 4 will quota sample from each strata with the aim of getting enough power to test H2.1: uptake is significantly correlated with method type; H2.2 uptake is significantly correlated with multi-methods.

Categories of PY	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
<= 2000	2,616	5.86	5.86
(2000 2005]	3,980	8.91	14.77
(2005 2010)	6,181	13.84	28.61
[2010 2015)	12,111	27.12	55.74
>= 2015	19,764	44.26	100.00
Total	44,652	100.00	

Stratification (June 10th)

/* 26 reviewers - 80 studies each to qualify as CA - minimum 2080 actual applications reviewed */

/* 5 methods categories; 5 periods approx. means approx. 84 studies per strata */

/* out of scope % of studies is unknown and needs to be determined during first stage */

strata_methods	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
biophysical(TS20)	420	20.00	20.00
integrating(TS23)	420	20.00	40.00
multi-method	420	20.00	60.00
revealed(TS22)	420	20.00	80.00
stated(TS21)	420	20.00	100.00
Total	2,100	100.00	

Hypothesis: H3.1 uptake has improved since pre MEA; H3.2 uptake has improved since TEEB

Categories of PY	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
<= 2000	420	20.00	20.00
(2000 2005]	420	20.00	40.00
(2005 2010)	420	20.00	60.00
[2010 2015)	420	20.00	80.00
>= 2015	420	20.00	100.00
Total	2,100	100.00	

Reviewer assignment distribution

Papers assigned systematically with each reviewer assigned the n+26th study, so that each reviewer reviews studies across all periods and method family strata.

(caveats: Reviewers work as generalists and are more able to evaluate uptake and purpose across disciplines. Lower efficiency in review because new methods types.)

Database of sample ch4 uptake review

This sample is to be distributed across the N reviewers, with a separate folder for each reviewer containing the pdfs of their assignment.

Questions -

1. Sampling efficiency. A straw poll of studies from the ch4 stratified sample above revealed a large proportion of non valuation non NCP-ES studies e.g. in the biophysical methods stratum. I fear that a lot of the sample will be out of scope, but still take up reviewer time in screening out these studies. This was not clear until I generated a stratified sample that was small enough for me to sift through manually.

Phase I. we should meet weekly for 2 weeks to see what proportion of studies are in scope.

2. Hypothesis testing. The keyword search has the problem of being highly inclusive. It does not discriminating for the purpose of hypothesis testing what explains uptake. The methods strata are still very broad. What is the universe we are testing the hypothesis of valuation uptake for? All studies, or those methods that have the intended purpose of decision-support? (e.g. the assumption that economic valuation is speaking money to power; or that deliberative valuation is more inclusive, or that benefit transfer is more applied).

Phase II. we should prepare for the possibility that within 2-3 weeks we need to generate a narrower corpus focused on valuation method applications which are “designed for decision-support”, and then test uptake.

3. Rapid action needed on refining uptake hypotheses and narrowing search terms for a narrower ch4 corpus.

STATA code to generate sample (June version)

The following STATA script was used to generate the sample for the Chapter 4 sample.

```
/******
```

```

/*          STATA CODE
*/
/*      IPBES VALUES ASSESSMENT  STRATIFIED SAMPLING  */
/*      JUNE 2020                                          */
/*
*/
/*****/

/* Manually reduce the size of the corpus. 40MB limit for STATA dataset */
/* In Excel delete all columns except AU TI  DI  PY  CountryName_TI_AB_DE_ID
CountryName_CI_FU_FX
TS17  TS18  TS19  TS20  TS21  TS22  TS23  TS24  TS25  TS26  TS27
*/

/* load data */
import excel "C:\Users\david.barton\OneDrive -
NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Raw\IPBES_VA_Uptake_Corpus_06May20_GEONames_TS_05June20_reduced.x
lsx", sheet("Sheet1") firstrow clear

/* DEFINITIONS */

/* TS18 C1_Method A          #17 AND #6  general valuation including benefit
transfer - do a targeted value transfer review later */
/* TS19 C2_Method B          #17 AND #7  qualitative and deliberative methods -
casual inspection of records shows this not to be reelvant universe for uptake as
intermediate methods*/
/* TS20 C3_Method_Family1 #17 AND #8  biophysical */
/* TS21 C3_Method_Family2 #17 AND #9  stated */
/* TS22 C4_Method_Family3 #17 AND #10 revealed */
/* TS23 C5_Method_Family4 #17 AND #11 integrating */

order DI PY AU  TI, first

/* Diagnostic - are papers applications in multiple method categories ?*/
gen method_number = TS20 + TS21 + TS22 + TS23 /* does the study use multiple methods
*/
gen no_application = 1 if method_number == 0 /*is the study not a methods
application? */
gen general_valuation = TS18*no_application /*non-applications with general
valuation keywords*/

/* Exclude from scope non-applications def. as studies with no method keywords */

drop if method_number == 0

/* Generate mutually exclusive methods strata */

gen strata_methods = "multi-method" if method_number > 1
replace strata_methods = "biophysical(TS20)" if TS20==1 & method_number == 1
replace strata_methods = "stated(TS21)" if TS21==1 & method_number == 1
replace strata_methods = "revealed(TS22)" if TS22==1 & method_number == 1

```

```

replace strata_methods = "integrating(TS23)" if TS23==1 & method_number == 1

tab strata_methods

/* Generate period strata, using katego command */

katego PY strata_period (2000 2005] (2005 2010) [2010 2015)

tab strata_period

/* generate IPBES region country strata */
/* not feasible to pre-stratify per June */
/* Can resample later to balance review for IPBES regions */

/* save revised corpus */

save "C:\Users\ david.barton\OneDrive - NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Temp\corpus_temp.dta",
replace

/* ESTIMATE OF MINIMUM SAMPLE SIZE CHAPTER 4 */
/* 26 reviewers - 80 studies each to qualify as CA - minimum 2080 actual applications
reviewed */
/* 5 methods categories; 5 periods approx. means approx. 84 studies per strata */
/* out of scope % of studies is unknown and needs to be determined during first stage
*/

/* GENERATE RANDOM STRATIFIED SAMPLE */
/* over methods and periods strata*/

use "C:\Users\ david.barton\OneDrive - NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Temp\corpus_temp.dta",
clear

sample 84, count by(strata_methods strata_period)

/* REMOVE STUDIES WITH MISSING Published year info */

drop if (strata_period ==.)

/* parse country names */

split CountryName_TI_AB_DE_ID, parse(,)

save "C:\Users\ david.barton\OneDrive -
NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Result\uptake_sample_june.dta", replace

/* describe strata */

tab strata_methods
tab strata_period

/*export only variables needed to identify the studies */

```

```
export excel DI PY AU TI CountryName_TI_AB_DE_ID CountryName_CI_FU_FX strata_methods
strata_period using "C:\Users\david.barton\OneDrive -
NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Result\uptake_sample_june.xls", firstrow(variables) replace
```

Approach (May version)

The May version of the corpus N=79040 has many studies with no method or value identifiers.

I considered the geolocators in title, abstract and keywords as too sparse to use as strata. I am not sure if I would biasing the sample by only using them and cleaning them up is taking some time with reviewers waiting for assignments.

I propose to post-stratify reviewed studies by IPBES region.

@Cem. For this reason we need an IPBES region coding question at the end of the ch4 Google Forms.

For this reason the sample was generated from the part of the corpus for which method type keywords were identified by chapter 3 (Nmethod= 13 283):

strata_methods	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
biophysical(T20)	6,335	8.01	8.01
integrating(T23)	767	0.97	8.99
other	65,757	83.19	92.18
revealed(T22)	5,044	6.38	98.56
stated(T21)	1,137	1.44	100.00
Total	79,040	100.00	

Some records have not publication date, so strata totals dont match:

Categories of pub_year	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
<= 1995	1,482	1.89	1.89
(1995 2005)	8,408	10.72	12.60
[2005 2015]	38,236	48.73	61.33
> 2015	30,340	38.67	100.00
Total	78,466	100.00	

Description of Chapter 4 sample by strata:

Running the script at the end of this note we produced the following stratified sample:

strata_methods	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
biophysical(T20)	720	26.85	26.85
integrating(T23)	605	22.56	49.40
revealed(T22)	720	26.85	76.25
stated(T21)	637	23.75	100.00

Categories	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Total	2,682	100.00	
<= 1995	524	19.54	19.54
(1995 2005)	720	26.85	46.38
[2005 2015]	720	26.85	73.23
> 2015	718	26.77	100.00
Total	2,682	100.00	

Reviewer assignment distribution

Distribution of the sample across reviewers can follow alternatives:

Alt.#1 Generalist reviewer. Papers assigned systematically with each reviewer assigned the n+26th study, so that each reviewer reviews studies across all periods and method family strata. Reviewers work as generalists and are more able to evaluate uptake and purpose across disciplines. Lower efficiency in review because new methods types.

Alt #2 Method specialist reviewer. Reviewers are assigned papers only within a single method stratum. More efficient reviewing because specialised, but benchmarks for uptake may be method internal

Preferred alternative for assignment distribution: #1 Generalist approach to promote cross method comparability, at the expense of reviewing efficiency.

Database of sample ch4 uptake review

This sample is to be distributed across the N reviewers, with a separate folder for each reviewer containing the pdfs of their assignment.

STATA code to generate sample

The following STATA script was used to generate the sample for the ch4 sample.

```

/*****
/*          STATA CODE
*/
/*      IPBES VALUES ASSESSMENT  STRATIFIED SAMPLING  */
/*          JUNE 2020
*/
/*****

/* Manually reduce the size of the corpus. 40MB limit for STATA dataset */

```

```

/* In Excel delete all columns except TI      DI      PY      SC      SR_FULL
   title_country abstract_country      keyword1_country      keyword2_country
   affiliation_country funding_country      funding2_country      GEO_Topic
   GEO_Fund      TS17      TS18      TS19      TS20      TS21      TS22      TS23      TS24      TS25      TS26
   TS27
*/

import excel "C:\Users\david.barton\OneDrive -
NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Raw\IPBES_VA_Uptake_Corpus_06May20_GEONames_29May_red.xlsx",
sheet("df25May") firstrow clear

/* DEFINITIONS */

/* TS18 C1_Method A      #17 AND #6 economic */
/* TS19 C2_Method B      #17 AND #7 qualitative */
/* TS20 C3_Method_Family1 #17 AND #8 biophysical */
/* TS21 C3_Method_Family2 #17 AND #9 stated */
/* TS22 C4_Method_Family3 #17 AND #10 revealed */
/* TS23 C5_Method_Family4 #17 AND #11 integrating */

order DI PY SR_FULL TI SC, first

/* Generate methods strata */

gen strata_methods = "biophysical(T20)" if TS20==1
replace strata_methods = "stated(T21)" if TS21==1
replace strata_methods = "revealed(T22)" if TS22==1
replace strata_methods = "integrating(T23)" if TS23==1
/* replace strata_methods = "other" if strata_methods == "" */

/* Generate period strata, using katego command */

destring PY, generate(pub_year) ignore("`NA'")
summarize pub_year, detail
katego pub_year strata_period (1995 2005) [2005 2015]

/* generate IPBES region country strata */
/* not feasible to pre-stratify per June */
/* Can resample later to balance review for IPBES regions */

/* save revised corpus */

save "C:\Users\david.barton\OneDrive - NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Temp\corpus_temp.dta"

/* ESTIMATE OF MINIMUM SAMPLE SIZE CHAPTER 4 */
/* 26 reviewers - 80 studies each to qualify as CA - minimum 2080 actual applications
reviewed */
/* Approximately a 33% non uptake rate found in training review */
/* Minimum expected assignment requirement total = 2860; */
/* 4 methods categories; 4 periods approx. means approx. 180 studies per strata */

/* GENERATE RANDOM STRATIFIED SAMPLE */
/* over methods and periods strata*/

```

```
use "C:\Users\ david.barton\OneDrive - NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Temp\corpus_temp.dta",
clear

sample 180, count by(strata_methods strata_period)

/* REMOVE STUDIES WITH MISSING STRATA INFO */

drop if (strata_period ==. | strata_methods == "")

save "C:\Users\ david.barton\OneDrive -
NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Result\uptake_sample_june.dta", replace

/*export only variables needed to identify the studies */
export excel DI pub_year SR_FULL TI strata_methods strata_period using
"C:\Users\ david.barton\OneDrive - NINA\StataWork\IPBES\Result\uptake_sample_june.xls",
firstrow(variables) replace
```